

KINKING MECHANICS IN COMPOSITES UNDER COMBINED LOADING

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ABSTRACT

An analytical approach has been developed for kinking mechanics under combined compression-torsion loading for unidirectional carbon fiber composite. Single fiber-matrix unit is considered by using a fiber deformation representation with fiber amplitude and fiber rotation. Kink band mechanics with combined loading can be described with a simultaneous increase in amplitude and rotation of fiber which generates instability. It has been observed that presence of shear stress increases misalignment in the fiber, which results in a decrease in compressive load. A 2 D micromechanical analytical model is developed to predict the peak compressive strength with the externally applied torsional load. Predictions from the model are compared with experimental results and finite element analysis.

1 INTRODUCTION

The effect of shear loading on the compressive response of unidirectional carbon fiber composites is of interest for a wide variety of structural applications. The earlier compressive failure prediction model for unidirectional composites including the effect of shear was presented by Budiansky and Fleck[1]. Subsequently, experimental [2] and 3D finite element based numerical models were presented in the literature[2,3].

Kink band failure modeling in the composite is summarized by Schultheisz and Waas[4,5] and broadly reviewed by Alix et al.[6]. Kink banding is classified as a microbuckling model, kinking and bending theory. The microbuckling analysis is done by Rosen[7]. Whereas Argon [8] was first to consider kinking. His model further modified by Budiansky and Fleck [1], Budiansky et al.[9], Fleck et al.[10], Zidek and Hollmeck[11] and Hann and Williams[12]. Fleck et al. proposed the bending theory [10], whereas further analysis is done by Kyriakides et al.[13], Lee and Waas[14], Chung and Weitsman[15], De Mories and Morques[16] and Sun and Wankijun[17]. To get the kink strength bending theory was used by Pimenta et al.[18] along with closed form solution. However in FEA results [19] peak load and yield point of the matrix were not the same due to elastic and yield point of the matrix, as there is elastic and plastic discretized model [20]. Paul and Waas[21] formulated 2 D micromechanics model as elucidated by Chung and Weitzman[15] and Pimenta et al.[19]. Lee and Waas[14] modeled combined loading and further Yerramalli and Waas[2] extended the combined compression-torsion model. It has been observed that the compressive strength of composite depends on the mechanical strength of fiber, matrix shear, volume fraction, fiber misalignment. Yerramalli and Waas[3] developed a 3-D FEA model for combined loading.

In the current study a 2 D analytical model for combined compression-torsion is developed to predict compressive strength due to remote shear strength. The analytical kinking failure model of a UD composite for the combined compression-torsion loading case is developed by extending the formulation of Paul and Waas [21] to include the torsional loads in to the instability analysis. Detailed analytical model presented in the successive sections followed by the comparison of results with experimental data and FEA results[2,3]. Finally concluded with remarks.

2 MICROMECHANICAL FORMULATION

Geometry:

In this study, a configuration of single curved fiber having thickness t^f and matrix having thickness $2t^m$ is considered as shown in figure 1.

Figure 1: Unit cell configuration.

A plane strain composite unit cell with a fiber volume fraction V of 50% is used for the modeling purpose is shown in figure 2. The shape of initial perturbation is taken as $\omega_0(x)$ and $\omega(x)$ is the displacement along transverse to the fiber direction is shown in figure 3.

Figure 2: Composite representation.

Figure 3:Initial and deformed shape of fiber.

Deformation of fiber:

Initial fiber imperfection $\omega_0(x)$ is expressed with a sin function having amplitude ξ_0 over $2l$.

$$\omega_0(x) = \xi_0 \sin \left[\frac{\pi x}{2l} \right]$$

When initial imperfect fiber is compressed, kink band is formed by change in the amplitude of initial fiber misalignment with rotation of fiber. Deflection of fiber is assumed to be hyperbolic tangent function with two constants, one for the amplitude ξ and other shape ζ .

$$\omega(x) = \xi \tanh[\zeta x]$$

Axial displacement of the matrix is assumed to be varying linearly in the transverse direction. The fiber modelled as an Euler-Bernoulli beam and the matrix as a nonlinearly elastic material. fiber strain, ϵ_x^f and the matrix shear strain is γ_{xz}^m as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \epsilon_x^f(x) &= \epsilon_0^f(x) - Zk(x) \\ &= \left(u_0' + \frac{1}{2}\omega'^2 - \frac{1}{2}\omega_0'^2 \right) - z\omega'' \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

$$\gamma_{xz}^m(x) = \frac{1}{(1-\nu^f)} (\omega' - \omega_0') \quad (2)$$

Matrix model:

Matrix is modelled as a non-linear shear response by using seventh order odd polynomial given in equation 3. Where G_m is shear modulus of matrix in elastic and η_0, η_1 and η_2 are the parameters to fit the shear test data of the matrix. Experimental shear response can be easily fit by using the polynomial function without any assumptions.

$$\tau_{xz}^m = G_e^m [\gamma_{xz}^m - \eta_0 (\gamma_{xz}^m)^3 + \eta_1 (\gamma_{xz}^m)^5 - \eta_2 (\gamma_{xz}^m)^7] \quad (3)$$

Approximation up to cubic is done for the purpose of getting peak-response and post-peak behaviour of the model is sufficient.

Axial loading:

The unit cell having contribution from the fiber as potential energy due to axial loading is,

$$\begin{aligned}\Pi &= U - W \\ \Pi &= \frac{1}{2} \int_0^l \{\sigma^f \epsilon_0^f\} dx - (-P)\Delta\end{aligned}\quad (4)$$

Where P is load and the end displacement $\Delta = u_0(l) - u_0(0)$ is given as,

$$\Delta = \int_0^l u_0' dx = \int_0^l \left\{ \frac{-P}{E_0^f A^f} - \left(\frac{1}{2} \omega'^2 - \frac{1}{2} \omega_0'^2 \right) \right\} dx \quad (5)$$

By using equation 5 in equation 4 and simplifying the above expression as follows. Potential energy can be written as,

$$\begin{aligned}\Pi &= \frac{1}{2} \int_0^l \{(-P) \epsilon_0^f\} dx - (-P) \int_0^l u_0' dx \\ \Pi &= \frac{1}{2} \int_0^l \left\{ (-P) \left(u_0' + \frac{1}{2} \omega'^2 - \frac{1}{2} \omega_0'^2 \right) \right\} dx - (-P) \int_0^l u_0' dx \\ \Pi &= \frac{1}{2} \int_0^l \left\{ (-P) u_0' + (-P) \left(\frac{1}{2} \omega'^2 - \frac{1}{2} \omega_0'^2 \right) \right\} dx - (-P) \int_0^l u_0' dx \\ \Pi &= \frac{1}{2} \int_0^l \left\{ (-P) \left(\frac{-P}{E_0^f A^f} - \left(\frac{1}{2} \omega'^2 - \frac{1}{2} \omega_0'^2 \right) \right) + (-P) \left(\frac{1}{2} \omega'^2 - \frac{1}{2} \omega_0'^2 \right) \right\} dx \\ \Pi &= \frac{1}{2} \int_0^l \left\{ \left(\frac{-P^2}{E_0^f A^f} \right) + (-2P) \left(\frac{1}{2} \omega'^2 - \frac{1}{2} \omega_0'^2 \right) \right\} dx\end{aligned}\quad (6)$$

Bending loading:

Contribution from fiber as potential energy due to bending loading is,

$$U = \frac{1}{2} \int_0^l \{E_0^f I^f (\omega'' - \omega_0'')^2\} dx \quad (7)$$

Where E_0^f is the fiber young's modulus and I^f is the moment of inertia of the fiber.

Torsional loading:

$$\begin{aligned}\Pi &= U - W \\ \Pi &= \frac{1}{2} \int_0^l \{\tau^f \gamma^f\} dx - T\theta \\ \Pi &= \frac{1}{2} \int_0^l \left\{ \frac{A^f G^f \rho \theta}{l} (\omega' - \omega_0') \right\} dx - T\theta\end{aligned}\quad (8)$$

Where $\tau^f = \frac{A^f G^f \rho \theta}{l}$, $\gamma^f = (\omega' - \omega_0')$, A^f is the area of the fiber, G^f is the Young's modulus of fiber, ρ is the radius, θ is the angle of rotation, T is the torque applied.

Shear energy:

Shear energy contributed by the matrix is given as,

$$U = \frac{1}{2} \int_0^l \{A^m G_1 (\omega' - \omega'_0)^2\} dx - \frac{\eta_0}{2} \int_0^l \{A^m G_2 (\omega' - \omega'_0)^4\} dx \quad (9)$$

Where $G_1 = \frac{G_e^m}{(1-\nu_f)^2}$, $G_2 = \frac{G_e^m}{(1-\nu_f)^4}$ and A^m is the area of the matrix.

Unit cell energy:

In the unit cell, potential energy is the contribution from fiber, matrix and the external work. Fiber consist of (axial, bending and torsional energy), where a matrix consist of (shear energy).

Total unit cell potential energy Π is,

$$\Pi = U - W$$

$$\Pi = \frac{1}{2} \int_0^l \left\{ \left(\frac{-P^2}{E_0^f A^f} \right) + (-2P) \left(\frac{1}{2} \omega'^2 - \frac{1}{2} \omega_0'^2 \right) + E_0^f I^f (\omega'' - \omega_0'')^2 + A^m G_1 (\omega' - \omega_0')^2 + \frac{A^f G^f \rho \theta}{l} (\omega' - \omega_0') \right\} dx - \frac{\eta_0}{2} \int_0^l \{A^m G_2 (\omega' - \omega_0')^4\} dx - T \theta \quad (10)$$

By substituting the value of ω and ω_0 from equation integrate with respect to x . Potential energy will depend on load P , amplitude ξ and shape parameter ζ of fiber displacement profile. Hence $\Pi = \Pi(P, \xi, \zeta)$. Equilibrium equations can be obtain by differentiating Π with respect to ξ and ζ and equating it to zero. Load P can be obtain by solving two equilibrium equations as,

$P = P_\xi(\xi, \zeta)$ and $P = P_\zeta(\xi, \zeta)$ The closeform solution can be obtained by solving two equations simultaneously using Mathamatica ,solutions are listed in Appendix A. Δ can be obtained by using triplet $\{P, \xi, \zeta\}$ corresponding to the equilibrium equation. Figure 4 and 5 shows surfaces form by $\{P, \xi, \zeta\}$ space having potential energy is stationary. Intersection of two surfaces form an equilibrium path given by points $\{\xi^\circ, \zeta^\circ\}$ have $P_\xi(\xi^\circ, \zeta^\circ) = P_\zeta(\xi^\circ, \zeta^\circ)$ Points $\{\xi^\circ, \zeta^\circ\}$ obtain the equilibrium configuration for given load P and use to calculate Δ .

Figure 4: Surface given by the function $P_\xi(\xi, \zeta)$.

Figure 5: Surface given by the function $P_z(\xi, \zeta)$.

Figure 6: Surface intersection given by the function $P_\xi(\xi, \zeta)$ and $P_z(\xi, \zeta)$.

Material properties:

As shown in Table 1 and Table 2 constituent properties of the carbon vinylester composite are obtained from Yerramalli and Wass [2].

	E_0^f (MPa)	μ_f (MPa)	r_0 (μm)	ν^f	V^f
Carbon fiber	276000	-	5	0.35	0.5
Vinylester	3585	1318	-	0.36	0

Table 1: Composite constituent properties of carbon fiber and vinylester.

	V^f	μf (MPa)	A	n
Vinylester	0	1318	65.44	7.9603

Table 2: Shear stress-strain curve using Ramberg-Osgood for pure vinylester resin[2].

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Results from the current model are elucidated using the properties given in Table1 and Table2.

1. Comparison with the literature:

a) Imperfection sensitivity:

Peak compressive strength for varying imperfection amplitude is obtained for zero angle of rotation using current model. From figure 7 it is observed that peak compressive stress varies nearly linear with the variation in initial imperfection for carbon fiber vinylester composites. Results of the current model are compared with Yerramalli and Waas [3].

Figure 7: Comparison of peak stress as function of initial imperfection.

b) Shear stress and axial compressive stress:

Combined loading compression-torsion is obtained for carbon fiber vinylester composite by varying shear stress using change in angle of rotation. It has been observed that peak compressive strength of the composite decreases with increasing in shear stress. Failure envelope for carbon vinylester composite having volume fraction 50% is shown in the figure 8 and compared the results of the current model with Yerramalli and Waas [2].

Figure 8: Comparison of Failure envelope of carbon/vinylester of 50% V_f .

2. Effect of combined loading on composites:

Effect of shear loading on composite is obtained and shown in figure 8. Analysis can be done for each angle of rotation from pure compression to pure rotation. Here we will do the analysis for carbon vinylester composite specimen as follows. Figure 9 shows axial strain and shear strain relation for 40 deg. angle of rotation having initial imperfection 2.3 deg. and volume fraction 50%.

Figure 9: Axial strain as a function of shear strain for 40 deg. angle of rotation.

Axial compressive and strain relation is shown in figure10. It is observed for the 40 deg. angle of rotation and 2.3 deg. initial imperfection that initially strain varies linearly upto peak compressive load then it attains nonlinearity due to non linearity in composites.

Figure 10: Axial stress vs strain for 40 deg. angle of rotation carbon-vinylester of 50% V_f .

Shear stress and shear strain relation is shown in figure 11. It is observed that shear strain varies non-linearly with shear stress due to non-linearity induced in the composite during shear stress.

Figure 11: Shear stress vs shear strain for 40 deg. angle of rotation of carbon-vinylester.

Axial compressive stress and shear stress relation is shown in figure 12. It is clear from the figure that initially shear stress varies linearly and varies non-linearly as shear stress increases.

Figure 12: Axial compressive stress vs shear stress for 40 deg. angle of rotation.

4 CONCLUSIONS

We have presented a new analytical micromechanical model for predicting the peak failure stress of unidirectional composites subjected to combined axial compression and torsional loading. Present analytical model can effectively predict the peak compressive load as well as the complete load-displace and torque-rotation response under combined loading. The model results were validated for the carbon vinylester composite material based on data from [2]. Present analysis indicates that remotely acting shear stress in composites degrade the compressive strength in a linear fashion. The composite compressive response is very nonlinear due to the presence of torsional loading and the model indicates that the nonlinearity is due to the nonlinearity of the matrix under shear loading.

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APENDIX A

Closed-form solution for P_ξ and P_ζ

$$\begin{aligned}
 P_\xi = & -((3\text{Coth}[l\zeta](-\frac{A^f G^f \theta \rho \text{Tanh}[l\zeta]}{2l} - \frac{1}{24l^2 \zeta} A^m G_1 (-3\pi^3 \xi^0 \text{Csch}[\frac{\pi^2}{4l\zeta}] \\
 & + 16l^2 \zeta^2 \xi \text{Tanh}[l\zeta] + 8l^2 \zeta^2 \xi \text{Sech}[l\zeta]^2 \text{Tanh}[l\zeta]) \\
 & + \frac{1}{35840l^6 \zeta^3} A^m G_2 \eta^0 (-7\pi^7 \xi^2 \xi^0 \text{Csch}[\frac{\pi^2}{4l\zeta}] \\
 & - 560l^2 \pi^5 \zeta^2 \xi^2 \xi^0 \text{Csch}[\frac{\pi^2}{4l\zeta}] - 7168l^4 \pi^3 \zeta^4 \xi^2 \xi^0 \text{Csch}[\frac{\pi^2}{4l\zeta}] \\
 & + 8960l^3 \pi^4 \zeta^3 \xi \xi^0 \text{Csch}[\frac{\pi^2}{2l\zeta}] - 3360l^2 \pi^5 \zeta^2 \xi^0 \text{Cosh}[\frac{\pi^2}{4l\zeta}]^2 \text{Csch}[\frac{3\pi^2}{4l\zeta}] \\
 & + 16384l^6 \zeta^6 \xi^3 \text{Tanh}[l\zeta] + 11264l^6 \zeta^6 \xi^3 \text{Sech}[l\zeta]^6 \text{Tanh}[l\zeta] \\
 & + 7168l^6 \zeta^6 \xi^3 \text{Cosh}[2l\zeta] \text{Sech}[l\zeta]^6 \text{Tanh}[l\zeta] \\
 & + 1024l^6 \zeta^6 \xi^3 \text{Cosh}[4l\zeta] \text{Sech}[l\zeta]^6 \text{Tanh}[l\zeta]) \\
 & - \frac{1}{480l^4 \zeta} E^f I^f (-15\pi^5 \xi^0 \text{Csch}[\frac{\pi^2}{4l\zeta}] - 120l^2 \pi^2 \zeta^2 \xi^0 \text{Sech}[l\zeta]^2 \\
 & + 512l^4 \zeta^4 \xi \text{Sech}[l\zeta]^2 \text{Tanh}[l\zeta]^3 \\
 & + 128l^4 \zeta^4 \xi \text{Cosh}[2l\zeta] \text{Sech}[l\zeta]^2 \text{Tanh}[l\zeta]^3)) / (\zeta \xi (2 + \text{Sech}[l\zeta]^2)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
P_\zeta = & (6(-\frac{1}{2}A^f G^f \theta \xi \rho \operatorname{Sech}[l\zeta]^2 - \frac{1}{96l^3 \zeta^3} A^m G_1(12l\pi^3 \zeta \xi \xi 0 \operatorname{Csch}[\frac{\pi^2}{4l\zeta}] \\
& - 3\pi^5 \xi \xi 0 \operatorname{Coth}[\frac{\pi^2}{4l\zeta}] \operatorname{Csch}[\frac{\pi^2}{4l\zeta}] + 32l^4 \zeta^4 \xi^2 \operatorname{Sech}[l\zeta]^2 \\
& + 16l^4 \zeta^4 \xi^2 \operatorname{Sech}[l\zeta]^4 + 32l^3 \zeta^3 \xi^2 \operatorname{Tanh}[l\zeta] \\
& + 16l^3 \zeta^3 \xi^2 \operatorname{Sech}[l\zeta]^2 \operatorname{Tanh}[l\zeta] - 32l^4 \zeta^4 \xi^2 \operatorname{Sech}[l\zeta]^2 \operatorname{Tanh}[l\zeta]^2) \\
& - \frac{1}{1920l^5 \zeta^3} E^f I^f (60l\pi^5 \zeta \xi \xi 0 \operatorname{Csch}[\frac{\pi^2}{4l\zeta}] \\
& - 15\pi^7 \xi \xi 0 \operatorname{Coth}[\frac{\pi^2}{4l\zeta}] \operatorname{Csch}[\frac{\pi^2}{4l\zeta}] - 480l^3 \pi^2 \zeta^3 \xi \xi 0 \operatorname{Sech}[l\zeta]^2 \\
& + 960l^4 \pi^2 \zeta^4 \xi \xi 0 \operatorname{Sech}[l\zeta]^2 \operatorname{Tanh}[l\zeta] + 3072l^6 \zeta^6 \xi^2 \operatorname{Sech}[l\zeta]^4 \operatorname{Tanh}[l\zeta]^2 \\
& + 768l^6 \zeta^6 \xi^2 \operatorname{Cosh}[2l\zeta] \operatorname{Sech}[l\zeta]^4 \operatorname{Tanh}[l\zeta]^2 \\
& + 3072l^5 \zeta^5 \xi^2 \operatorname{Sech}[l\zeta]^2 \operatorname{Tanh}[l\zeta]^3 \\
& + 768l^5 \zeta^5 \xi^2 \operatorname{Cosh}[2l\zeta] \operatorname{Sech}[l\zeta]^2 \operatorname{Tanh}[l\zeta]^3 \\
& + 512l^6 \zeta^6 \xi^2 \operatorname{Sech}[l\zeta]^2 \operatorname{Sinh}[2l\zeta] \operatorname{Tanh}[l\zeta]^3 \\
& - 2048l^6 \zeta^6 \xi^2 \operatorname{Sech}[l\zeta]^2 \operatorname{Tanh}[l\zeta]^4 \\
& - 512l^6 \zeta^6 \xi^2 \operatorname{Cosh}[2l\zeta] \operatorname{Sech}[l\zeta]^2 \operatorname{Tanh}[l\zeta]^4) \\
& + \frac{1}{4} A^m G_2 \eta 0 (-\frac{\pi^3(\pi^2 + 16l^2 \zeta^2) \xi^3 \xi 0 \operatorname{Csch}[\frac{\pi^2}{4l\zeta}]}{30l^4 \zeta^2} \\
& - \frac{\pi^3(\pi^2 + 64l^2 \zeta^2) \xi^3 \xi 0 \operatorname{Csch}[\frac{\pi^2}{4l\zeta}]}{120l^4 \zeta^2} \\
& + \frac{\pi^3(\pi^2 + 16l^2 \zeta^2)(\pi^2 + 64l^2 \zeta^2) \xi^3 \xi 0 \operatorname{Csch}[\frac{\pi^2}{4l\zeta}]}{1280l^6 \zeta^4} \\
& - \frac{\pi^5(\pi^2 + 16l^2 \zeta^2)(\pi^2 + 64l^2 \zeta^2) \xi^3 \xi 0 \operatorname{Coth}[\frac{\pi^2}{4l\zeta}] \operatorname{Csch}[\frac{\pi^2}{4l\zeta}]}{15360l^7 \zeta^5} \\
& + \frac{\pi^6 \xi^2 \xi 0^2 \operatorname{Coth}[\frac{\pi^2}{2l\zeta}] \operatorname{Csch}[\frac{\pi^2}{2l\zeta}]}{4l^4 \zeta^2} + \frac{3\pi^5 \xi \xi 0^3 \operatorname{Cosh}[\frac{\pi^2}{4l}]^2 \operatorname{Csch}[\frac{3\pi^2}{4l}]}{8l^4 \zeta^2} \\
& - \frac{9\pi^7 \xi \xi 0^3 \operatorname{Cosh}[\frac{\pi^2}{4l\zeta}]^2 \operatorname{Coth}[\frac{3\pi^2}{4l\zeta}] \operatorname{Csch}[\frac{3\pi^2}{4l\zeta}]}{32l^5 \zeta^3} + \frac{1}{35} l \zeta^3 \xi^4 \operatorname{Sech}[l\zeta]^2 (16 \\
& + 11 \operatorname{Sech}[l\zeta]^6 + 7 \operatorname{Cosh}[2l\zeta] \operatorname{Sech}[l\zeta]^6 + \operatorname{Cosh}[4l\zeta] \operatorname{Sech}[l\zeta]^6) \\
& + \frac{3\pi^7 \xi \xi 0^3 \operatorname{Cosh}[\frac{\pi^2}{4l\zeta}] \operatorname{Csch}[\frac{3\pi^2}{4l\zeta}] \operatorname{Sinh}[\frac{\pi^2}{4l\zeta}]}{16l^5 \zeta^3} + \frac{3}{35} \zeta^2 \xi^4 (16 + 11 \operatorname{Sech}[l\zeta]^6 \\
& + 7 \operatorname{Cosh}[2l\zeta] \operatorname{Sech}[l\zeta]^6 + \operatorname{Cosh}[4l\zeta] \operatorname{Sech}[l\zeta]^6) \operatorname{Tanh}[l\zeta] \\
& - \frac{2}{35} \zeta^3 \xi^4 \operatorname{Tanh}[l\zeta] (-7l \operatorname{Sech}[l\zeta]^6 \operatorname{Sinh}[2l\zeta] - 2l \operatorname{Sech}[l\zeta]^6 \operatorname{Sinh}[4l\zeta] \\
& + 33l \operatorname{Sech}[l\zeta]^6 \operatorname{Tanh}[l\zeta] + 21l \operatorname{Cosh}[2l\zeta] \operatorname{Sech}[l\zeta]^6 \operatorname{Tanh}[l\zeta] \\
& + 3l \operatorname{Cosh}[4l\zeta] \operatorname{Sech}[l\zeta]^6 \operatorname{Tanh}[l\zeta])) / (-2l \zeta \xi^2 \operatorname{Sech}[l\zeta]^2 \\
& - l \zeta \xi^2 \operatorname{Sech}[l\zeta]^4 - 2 \xi^2 \operatorname{Tanh}[l\zeta] - \xi^2 \operatorname{Sech}[l\zeta]^2 \operatorname{Tanh}[l\zeta] \\
& + 2l \zeta \xi^2 \operatorname{Sech}[l\zeta]^2 \operatorname{Tanh}[l\zeta]^2)
\end{aligned}$$